

Studies on the solubilities and dissociation constants of substituted benzoic acids in 2-propanol-water mixtures and ion-solvent interactions

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Abstract : The solvational behaviour of 2- and 3-substituted bromo- and iodo-benzoic acids have been examined from the solubility of the acids and the dissociation constants for the reaction

determined conductometrically using Fuoss-Kraus method in 2-propanol + water mixtures (0–87 mass% of 2-propanol). The changes in the solubility values depend on the hydrophobic character and the dielectric constant of the solvent medium. The Gibbs energy of transfer for anions have been determined from the relation

$$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{dissn.}) = \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{A}^-) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{HA})$$

using the previously determined values of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$. $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{A}^-)$ values have been found to be increasingly positive in aquo-organic mixtures and the $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{A}^-)$ values of the 3-compounds are considerably different from those of 2-compounds. The results are discussed in the light of solute-solvent interactions. The effects of substitution on the interaction energies of anions have been determined.

Keywords : Ion-solvent interaction, dissociation constant, benzoic acid, conductivity measurement.

Introduction

The importance of solute-solvent interactions and nature of solvation has been widely emphasized¹. Since most of the reactions of chemical and biological interest occur in solution, understanding of solvation phenomena demands extensive studies of the physical properties of electrolytes (weak and strong) and non-electrolytes in aqueous, mixed and non-aqueous solvents. Changes in the ion-solvent interactions on transfer of electrolytes between solvents are small but are sufficiently large to cause dramatic changes in chemical reactions involving ions and are of importance in elucidating reaction mechanisms in analytical chemistry, organic and inorganic synthesis, in biological processes etc.².

The solvent effects on the dissociation equilibria have been extensively studied by Lahiri and co-workers³⁻⁵. It is well known that Gibbs energy of transfer of an electrolyte like HX from water to other solvents may provide information on the effect of solvents on the dissociation processes but the information is inadequate to give satisfactory idea regarding ion-solvent interactions,

the compilation of which are necessary for the proper understanding of solvation phenomena.

It is known that the ion-solvent interactions cannot be calculated a priori nor they can be experimentally determined. Naturally, extra thermodynamic methods are necessary to get ideas about ion-solvent interactions⁶.

These considerations led us to determine the solubilities and the thermodynamic dissociation constants of different substituted benzoic acids (having antifungal activities) in different aquo-organic solvents. The values have been utilised to determine the Gibbs energy of transfer of the acids from aqueous to mixed solvents⁷⁻⁹ and their division into single ion values. The present work is an extension of such studies where the solubilities and the dissociation constants of benzoic acids (2- and 3-bromo- and iodo-) have been determined in 2-propanol + water mixtures (0–87 mass% of 2-propanol) from solubility and conductometric studies. The values have been utilized to obtain Gibbs energy of transfer of ions. The results have been presented in this paper.

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Experimental

2-Propanol (A.R., RDH) was treated with metallic sodium for 14 h, refluxed and distilled. The middle fraction was used. Triply distilled water was used for preparing the solutions. The mixed solvents were prepared by mixing the solvents by volume and converted into mass percentages using measured densities of the mixed solvents. The densities of the pure and mixed solvents were determined in the way reported earlier⁷ and the dielectric constants (ϵ) of mixed solvents were taken from the literature¹⁰.

Substituted benzoic acids (2- and 3-bromo- and iodo-) were of Fluka's Puriss grade and used as such. However, the compounds were heated in an air-oven at about 390 K for an hour and kept in a vacuum desiccator. The compounds were estimated volumetrically using phenolphthalein as indicator. Succinic acid, potassium hydrogen-phthalate, perchloric acid, sodium hydroxide and potassium hydroxide utilised in different stages of experiments, were of guaranteed quality from E. Merck or BDH (India). The potassium salts of the acids were prepared by mixing known amounts of KOH with a little excess of the acids. The salts were crystallized from aqueous-alcoholic mixtures and recrystallized from alcohol.

For the determination of solubility of an acid e.g. benzoic acid, saturated solution of the acid was prepared at about 2° above the experimental temperature i.e. 298 K. The clear solution, taken in a modified Campbell solubility apparatus¹¹, was allowed to equilibrate in a thermostat maintained at 298 ± 0.02 K for six hours. After equilibration, the apparatus was inverted in the thermostat so as to facilitate the filtration of saturated solution. A definite amount of the filtered solution was estimated in the usual way⁶⁻⁹.

Conductance measurements of the substituted benzoic acids and their potassium salts were done with a Kyoto Electronics Conductance Bridge (Model GM-115, made in Japan). A specially designed Kyoto Conductivity Cell was used for conductance measurements. The cell constant (1.009 cm^{-1}) was determined using KCl solutions in the way described by Jones and Bradshaw¹². For the determination of the dissociation constants of the acids, the conductances of the different concentrations of the acids, potassium salts of the acids (usually of the order of $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ to $9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) were measured. The

measurements were done at 298 ± 0.02 K using an oil thermostat. Data for HClO_4 and KClO_4 were utilized from the works in our laboratory⁸.

Results

The thermodynamic dissociation constant for the reaction

(A^- = substituted benzoate ion)

can be written as

$$K = \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} \times C_{\text{A}^-}}{C_{\text{HA}}} \times \frac{\gamma_{\text{H}^+} \times \gamma_{\text{A}^-}}{\gamma_{\text{HA}}} \quad (2)$$

γ represents the respective activity coefficients. In very dilute solutions, γ_{HA} can be reasonably assumed to be unity. The initial values of $\Lambda_{\text{o(HBz) Sub}}$ and K were obtained from the plot of ΔC against $1/\Lambda$ of a number of dilute solutions of HA utilising the equation

$$\Delta C = -K\Lambda_{\text{o}} + K\Lambda_{\text{o}}^2 / \Lambda \quad (3)$$

(neglecting activity coefficient values)

The accuracy of the method is known to be limited. Therefore, the method of computation suggested by Fuoss and Kraus¹³⁻¹⁵ was utilised. The equation utilised is

$$\frac{F(Z)}{\Lambda} = \frac{1}{K\Lambda_{\text{o}}^2} \times \frac{\Delta C \gamma_{\pm}^2}{F(Z)} + \frac{1}{\Lambda_{\text{o}}} \quad (4)$$

where

$$Z = \frac{(\theta\Lambda_{\text{o}} + \sigma) \sqrt{\Delta C}}{\Lambda_{\text{o}}^{3/2}} \quad (5)$$

The values of the Onsager constants σ and θ

$$\sigma = \frac{82.4}{(\epsilon T)^{1/2} \eta} \quad \text{and} \quad \theta = \frac{8.20 \times 10^3}{(\epsilon T)^{3/2}} \quad (6)$$

were calculated utilising η (viscosity)⁷ and ϵ (with suitable interpolations where necessary) values of the binary mixtures from the literature¹⁰.

$F(Z)$ can be calculated using the relation

$$F(Z) = 1 - Z (1 - Z(1 - \dots)^{-1/2})^{-1/2} \quad (7)$$

or can be obtained from the literature¹⁴.

The limiting Debye-Hückel equation was utilised to calculate γ_{\pm} in dilute solution ($\sim 10^{-3} \text{ M}$)

$$-\log \gamma_{\pm} = A\sqrt{\alpha C} \quad (8)$$

using appropriate value of A and

$$\alpha = \Lambda/\Lambda_0 \left(A = 1.823 \times 10^6 \frac{Z_i^2}{(\epsilon T)^{3/2}} \right)$$

The physical parameters are presented in Table 1.

The slopes and the intercepts from the plot of $F(Z)/\Lambda$ against $\Lambda C_{\gamma_{\pm}}^2/F(Z)$ were calculated graphically as well as using the method of least squares. The values of the slopes ($1/K\Lambda_0^2$) were accepted only when the values of the regression coefficients were better than 0.995.

Λ_0 -values obtained from the intercepts are generally regarded to be erroneous as the values correspond to large extrapolations. Instead of using Λ_0 -values thus obtained, accurate value of Λ_0 were determined using Kohlrausch's additivity rule using the relation

$$\Lambda_0(\text{HA}) = \Lambda_0(\text{HClO}_4) + \Lambda_0(\text{KA}) - \Lambda_0(\text{KClO}_4) \quad (9)$$

$\Lambda_0(\text{HClO}_4)$ and $\Lambda_0(\text{KClO}_4)$ were taken from the data previously determined.

Calculation of K and Λ_0 -values for few sets using Fuoss (1978)¹⁶ equation showed only marginal changes in the Λ_0 . Λ_0 obtained by Fuoss-Kraus or Fuoss¹⁶ plots differs considerably from Λ_0 -values obtained from (9). The equation of Fuoss¹⁶ was not utilised.

The solubility, pK-values and Λ_0 -values of the substituted acids are given in Tables 2 and 3 respectively.

It is known that the solubility is an equilibrium process. Since the saturated solutions of the substituted acids in the two solvents are in equilibrium with the same solid phases, their Gibbs energies are also equal².

$$\bar{G}_{i=w} = \bar{G}_i + RT \ln_w a_i(\text{satd}) = {}_s G_1^0 + RT \ln_s a_i(\text{satd}) \quad (10)$$

Table 1. Values of parameters of different 2-propanol + water mixtures at 298 K

2-Propanol (mass%)	$1/\epsilon \times 10^2$	Mole fraction of 2-propanol	Density (kg dm ⁻³)	σ	θ	A
0.0	1.27	0.000	0.99707	60.20	0.229	0.509
8.0	1.37	0.025	0.98054	43.38	0.225	0.568
16.3	1.50	0.055	0.96813	32.16	0.293	0.650
25.1	1.65	0.091	0.94868	25.57	0.338	0.751
34.3	1.86	0.135	0.93770	23.89	0.404	0.899
43.9	2.13	0.190	0.90317	23.39	0.495	1.101
54.0	2.52	0.260	0.87847	24.51	0.637	1.417
64.6	3.10	0.354	0.85407	27.89	0.870	1.934
75.8	3.87	0.485	0.82972	33.76	1.213	2.697
87.5	4.72	0.675	0.80497	42.98	1.634	3.633

Table 2. Solubilities (mol dm⁻³) (A) and pK-values (B) of substituted benzoic acids in 2-propanol + water mixtures at 298 K

2-Propanol (mass%)	Solubility (mol dm ⁻³)							
	2-BrC ₆ H ₄ COOH		3-BrC ₆ H ₄ COOH		2-IC ₆ H ₄ COOH		2-IC ₆ H ₄ COOH	
	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)
0.0	0.0214	2.81 (2.85)*	0.0084	3.79 (3.81)*	0.0104	2.82 (2.86)*	0.0086	3.82 (3.86)*
8.0	0.0294	3.13	0.0029	3.98	0.0119	3.19	0.0103	4.10
16.3	0.0378	3.32	0.0045	4.26	0.0225	3.42	0.0199	4.36
25.1	0.1079	3.71	0.0145	4.47	0.0741	3.91	0.0721	4.63
34.3	0.5067	4.06	0.0599	4.78	0.3499	4.30	0.2998	4.99
43.9	1.5411	4.38	0.1269	4.94	1.1199	4.63	0.7536	5.21
54.0	1.8199	4.77	0.2988	5.31	1.4771	5.10	1.2599	5.63
64.6	2.2121	4.98	0.3656	5.51	1.6989	5.33	1.5579	5.86
75.8	2.3509	5.22	0.4365	5.77	2.0198	5.62	1.6599	6.08
87.5	2.5299	5.56	0.4599	5.83	2.2668	5.86	1.7611	6.12

Table 3. Equivalent conductances at infinite dilution Λ_0 (S cm² mol⁻¹) of KClO₄, HClO₄, KA and HA at 298 K

2-Propanol (mass%)	HClO ₄	KClO ₄	KA				HA			
			(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)
0.0	414.0	138.4	107.1	106.3	105.6	105.1	382.9	382.1	381.4	380.9
8.0	348.4	109.2	91.1	89.0	87.7	85.0	330.3	328.2	326.9	324.2
16.3	266.7	79.5	69.5	67.3	64.6	62.5	256.7	254.5	251.8	249.7
25.1	220.6	62.4	56.7	53.6	48.9	47.9	214.9	211.8	207.1	206.1
34.3	163.6	59.5	46.6	42.8	38.1	36.8	150.7	146.9	142.2	140.9
43.9	138.6	48.9	33.2	31.2	25.9	24.3	122.9	120.9	115.6	114.0
54.0	106.3	39.3	31.9	29.3	22.6	21.4	98.3	95.7	89.0	87.8
64.6	74.7	34.6	29.8	27.1	20.4	18.2	69.9	67.2	60.5	58.3
75.8	71.8	30.2	26.5	25.0	17.5	16.0	68.1	66.6	59.1	57.6
87.5	56.7	27.0	25.9	24.0	16.5	14.6	55.6	53.7	46.2	44.3

(a) 2-Bromobenzoic acid, (b) 3-bromobenzoic acid, (c) 2-iodobenzoic acid and (d) 3-iodobenzoic acid.

Table 4. Gibbs energies of transfer for neutral benzoic acids $\Delta G_t^0(\text{HA})$ and for the dissociation of benzoic acids $\Delta G_t^0(1)$ in 2-propanol + water mixtures

2-Propanol (mass%)	$\Delta G_t^0(\text{HA})$ (eq. 12) (kJ mol ⁻¹)				$\Delta G_t^0(1)$ HA (eq. 13) (kJ mol ⁻¹)			
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)
8.0	0.37	0.46	0.33	0.44	2.55	1.84	2.88	2.26
16.3	1.40	1.55	1.91	2.87	3.59	3.16	3.71	3.09
25.1	4.00	4.45	4.86	5.26	4.79	3.08	4.95	3.01
34.3	7.84	7.97	8.71	8.80	3.71	1.98	3.98	2.18
43.9	10.59	9.83	11.60	11.08	3.51	1.88	4.04	2.00
54.0	11.01	11.96	12.28	12.35	5.73	2.16	6.22	3.42
64.6	11.49	12.45	12.62	12.88	6.46	2.99	7.33	4.44
75.8	11.64	12.89	13.05	13.04	7.19	3.48	8.06	4.93
87.5	11.82	13.02	13.34	13.18	7.17	1.92	7.25	3.19

Thus, the Gibbs energies of transfer of neutral acid is

$$\Delta G_t^0(\text{HA})_{\text{neut}} = {}_sG_{\text{HA(Sub)}}^0 - {}_wG_{\text{HA(Sub)}}^0 - 2.303 RT \log ({}_s a_i(\text{satd}) / {}_w a_i(\text{satd})) \quad (11)$$

$$\text{or } \Delta G_{t(\text{neut})}^0 = -2.303 RT \log {}_m \gamma_i \approx -2.303 RT \log C_s / C_w \quad (12)$$

${}_m \gamma_i$ represents the medium effect of the species 'i' in going from water to other solvents. Activity coefficients of substituted acid should be unity in the respective solvent systems (by convention). C_s and C_w are the molar concentrations of substituted acids in the respective solvents. However, the acids are expected to dissociate very slightly in binary solvent systems and appropriate corrections for the changed concentrations of substituted benzoic acids were made for their dissociation in aqueous and aquo + organic solvents. The corrections were found to be negligible in most cases.

The Gibbs energies of transfer for the dissociation of substituted benzoic acids were calculated from the equation^{2,8,9}.

$$\Delta G_t^0(1) = \Delta G_s^0(1) - \Delta G_w^0(1) = 2.303 RT \log \frac{{}_m \gamma_{\text{H}^+} \cdot {}_m \gamma_{\text{A}^-}}{{}_m \gamma_{\text{HA}}} \quad (13)$$

The expression (11) and (13) are the measures of the differences between solute-solvent interactions (of the species involved) in the two ideal reference states with the solute-solute or ion-ion interactions eliminated².

$\Delta G_{t(\text{neut})}^0$ and $\Delta G_t^0(1)$ values of the substituted acids are recorded in Table 4.

Discussion

The solubilities of substituted benzoic acids at 298

K in 2-propanol + water mixtures are presented in Table 2. The errors in the solubility measurements are within 0.1 to 0.4% (at higher percentages). The sequence of the solubilities of substituted benzoic acids in aqueous and binary mixtures is 2-Br- > 2-I- > 3-I- > 3-Br- i.e. 2-compounds are more soluble than 3-compounds but the sequence of solubility for bromo and iodo compounds is reversed in 2- and 3-positions.

As expected, the solubilities of the substituted benzoic acids increase with the increase in hydrophobic character of the aquo-organic solvents. The variations of the solubilities of the substituted benzoic acids in different solvents result from the differences in the cohesive forces of the like solute molecules and solute-solvent interactions of various types¹⁸. Substituents change the dipole-moments of solutes leading to the changes in dipole-dipole and dipole-induced-dipole interactions. Variations in solubilities of the acids are thus expected but no quantitative correlation is possible. However, the effect of substitution and the variation of the solvent effect on the Gibbs energy of transfer with increase in organic cosolvent are shown in Fig. 1. The variation of $\Delta G_t^0(\text{neut})$ [ΔG_t^0 represents the transfer Gibbs energy changes of neutral or undissociated acids from water to mixed solvents], $\delta\Delta G_t^0$, the change in ΔG_t^0 due to substituents i.e. [ΔG_t^0 (substituted benzoic acid) - ΔG_t^0 (benzoic acid)] with percentage of organic co-solvent is initially positive and

The dissociation constants of benzoic acids in non-aqueous and mixed solvents had been reported by a number of workers²⁰⁻²². Recently, Niazi *et al.*²⁰ reported the values of the dissociation constants of benzoic acid (BA) and nitrobenzoic acids (NBA) in EtOH-W and 1-PrOH-W mixtures. The experimental data had been analyzed with Lee and Wheaton conductance equation²³.

The values of Λ_o and pK_a of benzoic acids in water determined by Niazi *et al.*²⁰ are in agreement with the values given in the literature¹⁹. However, Niazi *et al.*²⁰ did not claim any improvement in Λ_o or pK_a -values using Lee-Wheaton or Fuoss (1978) equation. Rather Λ_o -values obtained using long extrapolations, are likely to be erroneous. Niazi *et al.*²⁰ found extrapolation to zero concentrations impossible in case of benzoic acids for 60 and 70 mass% of ethanol + water mixtures. Substituents like $-NO_2$ in the benzene nucleus should not cause much variation in the conductivity of the substituted acids as obtained by us. However, Λ_o -values of benzoic acids reported by Niazi *et al.*²⁰ are anomalous and erratic in aqueous and aquo-alcoholic solutions as will be evident from the comparison of Λ_o -values and [Λ_o (subs acid) - Λ_o (benzoic acid)] (in parenthesis) given below.

Λ_o and [Λ_o (subs acid) - Λ_o (benzoic acid)] values (in S cm² mol⁻¹)

Mass% of EtOH	Benzoic acid (BA)	2-Nitro-BA		3-Nitro-(BA)		4-Nitro-(BA)	
0	383.14	401.48		406.06		369.86	
10	298.24	301.88	(3.6)	315.45	(17.2)	336.93	(38.7)
20	274.32	190.74	(-83.6)	257.42	(-16.9)	274.30	(0.0)
30	201.11	184.11	(-17.0)	186.18	(-14.9)	226.06	(24.9)
40	133.45	141.45	(8.0)	144.61	(11.1)	173.15	(39.9)
50	107.35	91.65	(-15.7)	131.74	(24.4)	114.38	(7.0)
60	125.22	60.91	(-64.3)	102.46	(-22.7)	85.53	(-39.7)
70	130.48	29.98	(-101.5)	96.95	(-33.5)	97.23	(-33.2)

changes in the order : 2-bromo > 3-bromo > 2-iodo > 3-iodo but becomes negative subsequently depending on the nature of the substituents and the sequence is usually maintained. The cosolvent has adverse effects on ΔG_t^0 (neut) initially but facilitates solvation afterwards.

The pK -values of substituted acids are given in Table 2. The accuracy in pK values ranges from ± 0.01 in water to ± 0.03 at higher percentage of organic cosolvents. The pK values in water agree well with the literature values¹⁹.

From the data, the Λ_o -values of anions in water at 298 K are 33.32, 51.66, 56.24 and 20.64 for benzoate, 2-, 3- and 4-nitrobenzoates. Except for formate ion, conductances of monovalent organic ions like acetate etc. in water are usually in the range of 30-40. The values 51.66 and 56.24 appear to be high. Moreover, Λ_o -values are expected to decrease with increase in organic cosolvent. The abnormally high (more than 100) or low (even negative) Λ_o -values in aquo + ethanolic mixtures suggest that the Λ_o -values reported by Niazi *et al.* are not correct,

Fig. 1. Plots of $\delta\Delta G^0_t(\text{neut})$ of (a), (b), (c) and (d) against mass% of 2-propanol : (a) 2-BrC₆H₄COOH, (b) 3-BrC₆H₄COOH, (c) 2-IC₆H₄COOH and (d) 3-IC₆H₄COOH.

Bosch *et al.*²¹ determined the pK-values of several weak acids including 3-bromobenzoic acid in 2-propanol and 2-propanol + H₂O mixtures using potentiometric titration of acids by tetrabutylammonium hydroxide.

Bosch *et al.* assumed that the solvents S₁(water) and S₂(2-PrOH) interact to give a structure S₁₋₂ and in mixed solvents, three solvent structures S₁, S₂ and S₁₋₂ may co-exist. pK values in any solvent mixture has been assumed to be weighted average of the ones in three solvents i.e.

$$pK = \frac{n_1 pK_1 + n_2 pK_2 + n_{1-2} pK_{1-2}}{n_1 + n_2 + n_{1-2}} \quad (14)$$

n₁, n₂ and n₁₋₂ are the number of molecules of solute solvated by each of the three respective solvents. Potentiometric titration method is not capable of determining simultaneously pK₁, pK₂ and pK₁₋₂. pH measurement is unable to ascertain the preferential solvation of H⁺ ion in different solvents and can give no idea about the preferential solvation of anions and neutral molecules. Moreover, S₁₋₂ bond must be weak and bonding

Fig. 2. Plots of $\delta\Delta G^0_t(\text{non-el})$ of (a), (b), (c) and (d) against mass% of 2-propanol : (a) 2-BrC₆H₄COOH, (b) 3-BrC₆H₄COOH, (c) 2-IC₆H₄COOH and (d) 3-IC₆H₄COOH.

of a cation or anion with S₁₋₂ will mean the rupture of S₁ – S₂ bond. Thus, pK₁₋₂ is only imaginary due to non-existence of the species

Bosch *et al.* also derived an equation based on the erroneous assumption

$$S_1 + S_2 = 2S_{1-2} \text{ (not } S_{1-2}) \quad (15)$$

It is to be noted that overall number of molecules will always change if S₁₋₂ is formed and this should change continuously with increase in S₂ and thus the equation derived by Bosch *et al.* cannot be accepted. However, pK values at low percentages of organic solvent determined by Bosch *et al.* agree with our results. The values actually represent pK₁ as pK₁₋₂ (almost absent) and pK₂ is absent.

The pK values of substituted benzoic acids increase continuously with increase in organic solvent and become nonlinear above 20 mass% of 2-propanol.

Following Bates and Robinson²⁴, one can write

$$\Delta G^0_t(1) = \Delta G^0_t(\text{el}) + \Delta G^0_t(\text{nonel}) \quad (16)$$

Fig. 3. Plots of $\Delta G^{\circ}_x(A^-)$ subs benz acid against mass% of 2-propanol : (a) 2-BrC₆H₄COOH, (b) 3-BrC₆H₄COOH, (c) 2-IC₆H₄COOH and (d) 3-IC₆H₄COOH.

Fig. 4. Plots of $\Delta\Delta G^{\circ}_{x,int}(ion)$ against mass% of 2-propanol : (a) 2-BrC₆H₄COOH, (b) 3-BrC₆H₄COOH, (c) 2-IC₆H₄COOH and (d) 3-IC₆H₄COOH.

Table 5. Gibbs energy of transfer of anion $\Delta G^{\circ}_i(A^-)$ (molar) of substituted benzoic acid (in kJ mol⁻¹) in different 2-propanol + water mixtures at 298 K

2-Propanol (mass %)	$\Delta G^{\circ}_i(H^+)^a$	$\Delta G^{\circ}_i(Bz^-)^b$	$\Delta G^{\circ}_i(2-BrBz^-)$	$\Delta G^{\circ}_i(3-BrBz^-)$	$\Delta G^{\circ}_i(2-IBz^-)$	$\Delta G^{\circ}_i(3-IBz^-)$	$[\Delta G^{\circ}_i(A^-)_x - \Delta G^{\circ}_i(A^-)_c]$
8.0	1.16	1.45	2.55	1.84	2.88	2.26	-0.18
16.3	2.03	2.62	3.59	3.16	3.71	3.09	-0.37
25.1	3.60	3.67	4.79	3.08	4.95	3.01	-0.60
34.4	4.31	3.32	3.71	1.98	3.98	2.18	-0.84
43.9	5.15	3.93	3.51	1.88	4.04	2.00	-1.15
54.0	5.50	5.03	5.73	2.16	6.22	3.42	-1.48
64.6	5.63	6.20	6.46	2.99	7.33	4.44	-1.87
75.8	5.08	7.83	7.19	3.48	8.06	4.93	-2.33

Column 8 : Conversion of ΔG°_i (anions) from molar to mole fraction scale

$$[\Delta G^{\circ}_i(A^-)_x - \Delta G^{\circ}_i(A^-)_c] = 5.7 \log \frac{M_w d_s}{d_w M_s}$$

$$M_s = \text{Molar mass of the assorted solvent} = 100 \left(\frac{W_{org}}{60.1} + \frac{100 - W_{org}}{18.02} \right)^{-1}$$

d_s is given in Table 1.

^aRef. 29, ^bRef. 8

$\Delta G_t^0(\text{el})$ represents the electrostatic contributions due to ions (calculated using Born²⁵ equation) and should be the same for all benzoate ions as the radii of the benzoate ions are likely to be the same. The variation of non-electrostatic components

$$\delta\Delta G_t^0(\text{nonel}) = \Delta G_t^0(1) (\text{subs acid}) - \Delta G_t^0(1) (\text{benzoic acid}) \quad (17)$$

with solvent composition is shown in Fig. 2. $\delta\Delta G_t^0(\text{nonel})$ results from changed interactions and structural variation of the binary mixtures due to introduction of the substituents in the parent molecule. The peaks in the region 8–16 mass% and around 54 mass% of 2-propanol may be a reflection of the structural variations of water molecules with the addition of organic co-solvent.

Transfer Gibbs energy changes of electrolytes provide little idea regarding solvent-effects on solute-solvent interactions. But the transfer Gibbs energy changes of single ions give relative magnitudes of the differences in the ion-solvent interactions of ions which are the controlling forces in dilute solutions where ion-ion interactions are small. The single ion values of organic ions are more important as most of the compounds of biological interest are organic ions.

The single ion values $\Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-)$ for the substituted benzoic acids can be obtained from the relation :

$$\Delta G_t^0(1) = \Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-) - \Delta G_t^0(\text{HA}) \quad (18)$$

$$\text{or, } \Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-) = \Delta G_t^0(1) - \Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_t^0(\text{HA}) \quad (19)$$

$\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ values have been taken from the works in our laboratory²⁶. The method has been extensively elaborated in our papers^{6,26–28}. The values of $\Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-)$ are recorded in Table 5. The accuracy of $\Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-)$ depends on the accuracy of $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ ions as the uncertainties in the experimentally determined $\Delta G_t^0(\text{HA})$ and $\Delta G_t^0(1)$ are very small. $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ ²⁶ values have been determined using extrathermodynamic assumptions with inherent limitations. The literature does not provide the accuracy of the single ion values but the accuracy of $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ can be assumed to be $\pm 0.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ value based on solvent sorting equilibrium are limited to 44 mass% of 2-propanol²⁹. But Well's method is defective and can in no way give $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$ ^{30,31}.

Naturally, it is difficult to predict the error involved in

$\Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-)_{\text{sub}}$ and the single ion values can never be exact. But, the sequence of $\Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-)$ values with increasing organic cosolvent is quite consistent and reliable. $\Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-)$ values have been found to be predominantly positive, a fact generally observed in practice^{7–9,24,29,30}. It is expected that the stabilization of anion due to hydrogen bonding in aqueous system decreases as we go from aqueous to aquo-organic solvents of decreased hydrogen bonding capability and increased basicity.

$\Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-)$ values (Fig. 3) of the 3-compounds are considerably different from those of 2-compounds obviously due to *ortho* effect. However, $\Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-)$ show maxima in the region of 16–75 mass% and 64–75 mass% of 2-propanol probably due to initial structure formation of water with addition of 2-propanol, subsequent depolymerization of water structure and gradual replacement of water structure by 2-propanol structure.

The Gibbs energies of transfer of molecules and ions usually give quantitative measure of solute-solvent or ion-solvent interactions. From extensions of the scaled particle theory³¹ to the electrically charged ions, we have

$$\Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-) = \Delta G_t^0(\text{cav})(\text{A}^-) + \Delta G_{t,\text{int}}^0(\text{A}^-) + \Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^0(\text{A}^-) + RT \ln \frac{V_w}{V_m} \quad (20)$$

where, $\Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-)_{\text{cav}}$ = Gibbs energy change due to cavity formation, $\Delta G_{t,\text{int}}^0(\text{A}^-)$ = Gibbs energy change due to interaction of ions with solvents, $\Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^0(\text{A}^-)$ = Gibbs energy change due to electrostatic interactions, V_w and V_m = molar volumes of water and mixed solvent respectively.

The calculation of $\Delta G_{t,\text{cav}}^0$ and $\Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^0$ may not be quite correct but $\Delta G_{t,\text{cav}}^0 \text{A}^-$ and $\Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^0 \text{A}^-$ can be considered to be equal for all benzoate ions.

Thus one can write,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\Delta G_{t,\text{int}}^0(\text{ion})_{\text{sub}} &= \Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-)_{\text{sub}} - \Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-) \\ &= \Delta G_{t,\text{int}}^0(\text{A}^-)_{\text{sub}} - \Delta G_{t,\text{int}}^0(\text{A}^-) \\ &= [(\Delta G_t^0(1)(\text{HA})_{\text{sub}} - \Delta G_t^0(1)(\text{HA}) + \\ &\quad (\Delta G_t^0(\text{HA})_{\text{sub}} - \Delta G_t^0(\text{HA}))] \quad (21) \end{aligned}$$

i.e. the change in the interaction energies of ions due to substituent can be obtained from the experimentally

determined quantities and depend only on uncertainties in experimental determinations. The plot of $\delta\Delta G_{t,int}^0$ (ion) against solvent composition (Fig. 4) gives the variation of interaction energies of ions due to substituents with variation of solvent compositions.

The values are predominantly positive for 2-compounds but predominantly negative for 3-compounds from 25 mass% 2-propanol and onwards.

Some fluctuations in the values are unavoidable.

But it is desirable to have more data for proper analysis and better insight on ion-solvent interactions.

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